

Speculation on Relativistic Momentum/Energy from Information and Space-Time Part II

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In Part I, we tried to obtain the special relativistic expression $E^2 - pc^2 = m_0^2 c^4$ ((1)) by considering a matrix made of two orthogonal row vectors $(x,0)$ $(0,ct)$. We multiplied by $m(v)/c$ and set $x/t=v$ =constant. Here $m(v)$ is taken to be mass as seen in a frame moving at a speed of $-v$. We then considered the matrix made of the two row vectors $(0,0)$ and $(0,m_0)$ and tried to find a connection between the two based on information. We suggested that whether one has a frame moving with $-v$ or v , one still has the same physical system with m_0 and no motion. Given that m_0 has no direction, we suggested multiplying one matrix with v with the same matrix with $-v$, taking the trace, and equating this with the trace of the $(0,0)$ $(0,m_0)$ matrix multiplied by itself. This led to ((1)).

Here we ask: Why were only linear quantities considered? X, t and m_0 as well as $m(v)$ are all taken to be linear. We suggested in Part I that these are physical quantities which are readily observable or measurable, but taking powers (or a function) of these is also possible and would lead to a different expression than ((1)). Why would such an expression be invalid? We suggest here that in the case of x and t linked to v (which is really dx/dt), translational invariance is key. In the case of m_0 , we suggest that conservation is key. In other words, two particles with masses $m_1+m_2=m_0$ sitting next to each other are equivalent to a single particle with m_0 . We suggest creating vectors (x,ct) and (pc, E) . p and E are linear in m_0 . If one uses another function of m_0 , then an expression of the form of ((1)) still holds (because m_0 ultimately factors out), but adding (pc,E) for m_1 and (pc,E) for m_2 with a power of m used, does not lead to a summand vector representing (m_1+m_2) to a power. This idea is not trivial we argue because it is linked with p which should be a conserved quantity. Thus, we want to be sure that it is linked with a linear m_0 and a factor v (due to translational invariance).

We also consider the quantum free particle situation and argue that a linear p applies for the same reason. It is linked to conservation of p which holds both classically and quantum mechanically.

Linear Quantities in $E^2 - pc^2 = m_0^2 c^4$

In Part I, we noted that objects in 3-space are usually described by the orthogonal vectors $(x,0,0)$, $(0,y,0)$ and $(0,0,z)$ and we used this to write two orthogonal vectors $(x,0)$ $(0,ct)$. (We gave reasons in Part 1 for using c , the speed of light in a vacuum.)

We then proceeded to develop the relationship:

$$E^2 - pc^2 = m_0^2 c^4 \quad ((1))$$

$$\text{where } E = \frac{m_0 c^2}{\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}} \text{ and } p = \frac{m_0 v}{\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}} \quad ((2))$$

In principle, one could physically describe an object in space by $(xx,0,0)$ $(0,yy,0)$ and $(0,0,zz)$ or any other power or function of the variables x,y,z . Why is this not done? We argue that the reason is translational invariance. A given x is measured from an origin and one may shift this

origin so that $x \rightarrow x+d$. One does not use vectors to simply describe an object, rather one may add or subtract them. For example, $(x_2,0,0) - (x_1,0,0)$ yields the distance between the x points and this should be invariant under a translational shift. If one uses some function of x , this invariance is lost. We suggest that this is the reason for using linear x and t .

What does one do in the case of rest mass? Rest mass is not associated with a translational shift. It is linked with the difficulty in lifting an object (gravitational mass) which should equal inertial mass. Why should one use a linear form of m_0 in ((1))? One may note that in ((1)), m_0 cancels from both sides so one may replace it with any function $f(m_0)$.

We argued in Part I that if one had no concept of energy and momentum, but only knew x, t and m_0 , one could derive the form ((1)), which leads to definition/emergence of the new quantities energy and momentum. These arise from comparing a description in a rest frame with a product of matrix descriptions in a frame moving with $-v$ and v (both constant). In other words, a matrix is created using the row vectors $(m(v)v/c, 0)$ and $(0, m(v))$. This is multiplied by the same matrix, but with $-v$. The trace is then equated to the product of the matrix with row vectors $(0,0)$ $(0,m_0)$ with itself. This leads to ((1)) and the definitions of energy and momentum as:

$$E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \quad ((3a)) \quad \text{and} \quad p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \quad ((3b))$$

We ask: Why could one not have used $f(m_0)$ instead of m_0 ? This would lead to different definitions of energy and momentum, but the form of ((1)) would still be preserved.

We suggest that the idea again goes back to vectors and additivity which is linked to conservation. We used $(0, m_0)$ as a vector in the matrix with row vectors $(0,0)$ $(0,m_0)$ in Part I. By using a linear form of m_0 , for $v=0$, $E=m_0 c^2$, if one adds two rest masses, E values add as well. This same property holds for a v (velocity case). We showed in Part I that one may multiply the vector $(0, m_0 c^2)$ by a Lorentz transformation matrix to obtain (pc, E) . In principle, one may break m_0 into two pieces m_i, m_j , such that $m_i+m_j=m_0$. If a function $f(m_0)$ is used instead of m_0 in ((3)), then $E(m_i)+E(m_j)$ would not equal $E(m_0)$. We suggest that a linear m_0 is used for reasons of creating the notion of conservation in the newly defined quantities E and p .

E and p and Conservation

$m_i+m_j = m_0$ is a conservation statement. It is also associated with force (a push or pull) which is required to measure m_i , whether one uses gravitational mass or inertial mass. Furthermore, even though moving frames were used above, physically one may set a particle with m_0 in motion by also applying a force. To be consistent, we suggest that the quantities E and p defined above should also exhibit conservation or add, i.e. $E(m_i)+E(m_j)=E(m_i+m_j)$ and a similar result for p . In other words, one does not have the choice to use an arbitrary function $f(m_0)$ in ((3)).

One may next consider the collision of two particles. Before the collision, they would have vectors (p_1c, E_1) , (p_2c, E_2) and after the collision (p_3c, E_3) , (p_4c, E_4) . One may add the two vectors before and after and ask whether momentum and energy should be conserved.

It is possible that one might have a physical collision in which both total E and p are conserved. In Part I, however, we established that a photon may have an energy. This suggests that there are other forms of energy than just the motion of a rest mass m_0 . Rest mass itself is a

form of energy. Sound should be another. Thus, there are physical ways to lose energy in a collision, such as the production of sound. One would therefore not expect that rest mass motion energy (kinetic energy) is conserved overall in general. Total energy (i.e. including sound etc, should be conserved.)

What about the case of momentum? Sound has energy and is moving and so should have momentum as well. One might imagine two particles colliding and producing sound as well as p_3 and p_4 values. Kinetic energy is lost to sound. Sound should have momentum, so one might argue that some net momentum is carried away by sound and p_1 plus p_2 (vectors) does not equal p_3 plus p_4 (vectors). The problem with this idea is the situation of time reversal symmetry. If two particles collide and create sound, then the time reversed situation, even with sound coming in, should produce more sound. It does not seem reasonable to say that p_3 and p_4 colliding (even with net sound waves coming in) cannot create new sound waves when colliding. In general, these would not have momentum which cancels. Furthermore, it is not clear how sound waves would be completely absorbed by a particle and converted into motional momentum as sound waves exist in a medium. As a result, conservation of motional momentum $p = mv / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ seems to apply.

Quantum Free Particle

We next consider the case of a quantum free particle, described by $\exp(-iEt)\exp(ipx)$. We notice again that p appears linearly, but multiplied by x . We argued in (1) that one may obtain $\exp(ipx)$ by maximizing Shannon's entropy subject to a constraint $\int g(p) P(x)$, i.e.

$$- \int P(x) \ln(P(x)) + i \int g(p) x P(x) \rightarrow P(x) = \exp(i g(p) x) \quad ((4))$$

i is used to make the probability periodic because it should not grow or decline indefinitely. In (1), we argued that one may set $g(p)$ to p because one has equal probability to have any p given a $P_{\text{spatial}}(x) = dx/L$. (Note: $P_{\text{spatial}}(x) = P^*(x)P(x)$.) The question is: Why does one use a linear p ? One could describe a particle by using any function of p in one dimension. If one wishes to distinguish the sign of p , one may use any odd function. We argue that a key point is conservation.

One may note that $P(x)$ is an eigenfunction of $-i d/dx$, where d/dx is the translational operator. Thus, this operator describes how the particle moves in space, but in what sense? We argue that it is in the sense of a conserved quantity. Thus, $E - pc = \text{momentum}$ uses a linear m in order to create an E and p which are/may be conserved. One may create vectors (pc, E) and (x, ct) and create the dot product $-Et + px$ in special relativity and this exact form appears in $\exp(-iEt + px)$, the free particle wavefunction. We argue that the reason is due to conservation in both cases.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in Part I we developed a scheme of multiplying two matrices with variable $m(v)$, x/t (v and $-v$ for the two matrices) and taking the trace and equating it to the trace of a product

of identical matrices containing m_0 . We found the relationship: $E^2 - p^2 c^2 = m_0^2 c^4$ which defines two entities:

$E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ and $p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$.

In this note we ask why a linear form of x, t and m_0 were used. We suggest that x and t in linear form allow for translational invariance, i.e. one may change the origin of x , but $x_2 - x_1$ remains the same, while it would not do so for some other function. The same argument applies to t , but not to m_0 .

We argue that m_0 , rest mass, is measured using force (gravitational) or a force measuring inertial mass. m_0 is additive, so the action of the force is additive. A particle is also set into motion using a force and so to be consistent, we argue that E and p should also be additive. This then becomes associated with conservation. We suggest that in general there are other forms of energy than kinetic $E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ and so kinetic energy is not necessarily conserved in a collision of particles, but argue for conservation of the total initial and final momentum.

Finally, we consider the case of a quantum free particle wavefunction $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ and ask: Why is a linear E and p used? We suggest that it is because of conservation again. The translational operator d/dt and d/dx (partial) describe how the particle moves in space in terms of a conserved quantity. This is linked to Fermat's least time principle which is also associated with momentum conservation in a direction in which there is no impulse, even though at first it seems to only be about time minimization.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Spatial Invariance, Information, Fisher Information and Fermat's Least Time Principle (preprint, zenodo, 2024)